

FRIENDSHIP IN KHALED HOSSEINI'S THE KITE RUNNER

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Abstract: In this article, the friendship between Amir and Hasan, which is impressively depicted in the work of Khalid Hosseini, one of the best works, "Kite Runner", its consistent realities, mistakes and regrets, friendship is better than anything in any situation, will be covered. Friendship is a major theme in The Kite Runner. The story follows Amir and his interactions with his father (Baba), best friend and servant (Hassan), and Hassan's father (Ali). The friendship between Amir and Hassan is like a brotherhood, which Hosseini crafts through plot, dialogue, and character development. In this lesson, we will look at the friendship theme through quotes that highlight friendship.

Key words: friendship, protagonist ,privileged, Afghanistan, cultural disparities, freedom and innocence, political and ethnic, betrayal

INTRODUCTION

“This powerful first novel, by an Afghan physician now living in California, tells a story of fierce cruelty and fierce yet redeeming love...In The Kite Runner, Khaled Hosseini gives us a vivid and engaging story that reminds us how long his people have been struggling to triumph over the forces of violence – forces that continue to threaten them even today.”

—The New York Times Book Review

Khaled Hosseini's novel, *The Kite Runner*, offers a poignant exploration of friendship and its complexities in the context of war-torn Afghanistan. The story revolves around the lives of two central characters, Amir and Hassan, who share a unique bond that transcends the confines of societal expectations and cultural disparities. Through their portrayal, Hosseini sheds light on the intricate dynamics of friendship and the sacrifices it often demands.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The connection between Amir and Hassan goes beyond a typical friendship. They share experiences such as nursing from the same woman and growing up together in the same home. Both of these boys are so intimately connected to one another that the only thing separating them is social status, with Hassan being Amir's servant. Amir, the protagonist, comes from a privileged background, while Hassan is his loyal Hazara servant and closest companion. Despite their different social positions, the two boys form an inseparable bond during their childhood in Kabul. They share a love for kite flying, a sport that serves as a metaphor for the freedom and innocence of their friendship. However, their relationship is not without its challenges.

RESULTS

One of the central conflicts in the novel stems from Amir's betrayal of Hassan. Unable to confront his own guilt and shame, Amir frames Hassan for theft, which ultimately leads to the rupture of their friendship. This betrayal echoes the broader political and ethnic tensions in Afghanistan, mirroring the disintegration of a country torn apart by conflict.

Hosseini's portrayal of friendship in *The Kite Runner* showcases the profound impact it can have on individuals and the lengths they go to repair what is broken. After the Soviet invasion forces Amir and his father to flee Afghanistan, he is haunted by his past actions and the loss of his childhood friend. The guilt drives him to embark on a redemptive journey back to his home country.

Upon his return to Kabul, Amir encounters the aftermath of war and the Taliban regime. The streets are filled with devastation and fear, yet through his pursuit of

redemption, he finds a way to atone for his past misdeeds. Hosseini highlights the power of friendship's potential for healing and transformation, as Amir dedicates himself to rescuing Hassan's son, Sohrab, who faces similar abuse and violence.

DISCUSSION

Hosseini draws on his own experiences growing up in Afghanistan and his subsequent exile to develop nuanced characters who reflect the complexities of friendship in a war-torn society. The author's detailed and vivid descriptions provide readers with a glimpse into the vibrant beauty of pre-war Kabul and the tragedy that befalls it.

Critics have commended Hosseini's ability to portray friendship in a humanizing and relatable manner. His writing captures both the joys and the challenges of deep connections, allowing readers to empathize with the characters' struggles and triumphs. By intertwining personal narratives with larger historical events, such as the Soviet invasion and the rise of the Taliban, Hosseini offers a compelling exploration of the impact of external forces on individuals and their relationships.

CONCLUSION

Khaled Hosseini's *The Kite Runner* is a compelling portrayal of friendship's complexities within the backdrop of a war-torn Afghanistan. Through the friendship between Amir and Hassan, Hosseini crafts a story that explores themes of guilt, betrayal, and redemption, leaving readers with a profound understanding of the enduring power of friendship in the face of adversity.

“A marvelous first novel... an incredible story of the culture. It’s an old-fashioned kind of novel that really sweeps you away.”

—San Francisco Chronicle

Social class refers to the social order of a group of people within a society; it encompasses many aspects of their lifestyle, including their wealth, power, and culture. In Khaled Hosseini's novel *The Kite Runner*, the narrator, Amir, is blessed with status from birth, but things change when he emigrates to America.

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